

Changes in grain dry weight and water content of rice stressed at different stages after panicle emergence.^a

PE ^b before maximum WD ^c (d)	Cultivar	Change in dry weight		Change in water content		Water loss and dry weight relationship	
		(mg/d)	r	(%/d)	r	slope	r
20-25	AUS257	1.8	0.97**	3.8	0.98**	-0.33	0.97**
15-19	AUS196	1.4	0.98**	5.5	0.99**	-0.27	0.92**
15-19	UPLRI-7	1.7	0.96**	2.5	0.99**	-0.43	0.95**
10-14	AUS257	0.8	0.88*	3.3	0.99**	-0.41	0.98**
10-14	IRAT104	2.4	0.98**	4.2	0.91**	-0.82	0.92**
5-9	IR43	1.1	0.98**	2.4	0.99**	-0.42	0.96**
0-4	UPLRI-7	1.7	0.99**	1.9	0.98**	-0.68	0.99**
0-4	UPLRI-7	1.7	0.98**	1.8	0.99**	-0.80	0.96**
SD		0.45		1.2		0.20	

*, ** = significant and highly significant, respectively, at the 5% level. ^aPE = panicle emergence. ^bWD = water deficit.

emergence period of 10-14 d before maximum water deficit, AUS257, a small-seeded cultivar, increased grain dry weight by 0.8 mg/d while IRAT104, a large-seeded cultivar, increased its

grain dry weight by 2.4 mg/d (see table).

Except for AUS257, water content was almost constant until 5-6 d after panicle emergence, after which it decreased almost linearly. At harvest,

grain water content ranged from 10 to 30% (see figure). Rice grain lost less water when panicle emergence was close to maximum water deficit (UPLRI-7 grain lost 1.8% water/d) than when panicles emerged between 15 and 19 d before maximum water deficit (grain lost 2.5% water/d). IRAT104 lost 4.2% water/d compared with AUS257, which lost only 3.3% water/d, even though their panicles emerged within the same period.

Grain water content and grain dry weight were negatively correlated (see table). The leveling off in dry weight was not accompanied by leveling off in water content because water loss continued for a few more days. These findings suggest that even if grain is fully mature, it continues to lose water even under water deficit. Results also suggest that a decrease in water loss in the grain was due to low water status during water deficit and not mainly to maturation. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Kairala (Ptb49), a high-yielding rice variety with multiple resistance from Kerala, India

C. A. Rosamma, C. R. Elsy, V. P. S. Dev, and K. M. Rajan, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India

Popular high-yielding rice varieties of Kerala—Jyothi, Pavizham, and Annapoorna—were crossed with highly adaptable IR36 in a breeding program to develop varieties with multiple resistance to pests. Single plants with desired attributes were selected from the segregating population.

KAU8754, a promising culture isolated from the cross IR36/Jyothi, showed high yield potential and moderate to high levels of resistance to leaf blast, neck blast, sheath blight, gall midge biotypes 1 and 4, and whitebacked planthopper. This elite line was released as Kairali (Ptb49) in 1993.

The variety was highly promising in station trials from 1987 to 1991, with a mean yield of 4.1 t/ha. In the 1991-92 kharif (dry) season, the variety yielded a

mean of 5.2 t/ha across 23 locations in the All India Coordinated Trials, indicating high adaptability to different soil and environmental conditions (see table). The mean yield of Kairali was 500 kg/ha higher than Ratna, the check variety.

Grain is long bold with red kernels. Milling and cooking qualities are excellent.

Performance of Kairali at different sites in India.

Location	Mean grain yield (t/ha)	
	Kairali	Ratna
Kerala	4.7	4.1
Tamil Nadu	5.4	5.5
Karnataka	4.7	4.1
Andhra Pradesh	4.6	4.0
Maharashtra	3.2	2.8
Haryana	6.8	6.3
Rajasthan	5.4	5.4
Punjab	5.0	4.3
Jammu and Kashmir	5.5	4.0
Mean ^a	5.2	4.7

^aMean of two seasons at 23 locations.

With a duration of 110-115 d, the variety is recommended for all three rice-growing seasons of Kerala (kharif, rabi [wet], and summer). ■

Zhefu No. 9, a new indica rice variety in central and eastern China

Xia Yinwu and Shu Qingyao, Institute of Nuclear Agricultural Sciences, Zhejiang Agricultural University, Hangzhou 310029, China

Zhefu No.9, derived from cross 44-1086/IR50, was released in Apr 1993 for use as an early season (April to July) indica variety in the double-cropped area of central and eastern China.

Zhefu No. 9 is a short-duration, semidwarf indica rice. It is 80-85 cm tall and has 105-110 d growth duration. Average yield is about 6.6 t/ha under normal cultivation and maximum yield is 8.8 t/ha under high fertilization and good management, which was 8.1-18.7% and 4.3-20.1% more than the checks,